

THE ROLE OF STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITY REPUTATION AND PR

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Abstract. This article explores the significant role that students play in shaping the reputation and public relations (PR) efforts of universities. By examining the influence of student activities, organizations, and projects on the overall image of educational institutions, this research aims to shed light on the impact of student engagement on university reputation management. Through a comprehensive analysis of student involvement in various extracurricular activities, social projects, and PR campaigns, this study seeks to identify key strategies and successful case studies that demonstrate how students can effectively contribute to enhancing the reputation of their universities. By highlighting the importance of student interaction with society and their role as brand ambassadors for their institutions, this research provides valuable insights for university administrators, PR professionals, and students themselves on leveraging student initiatives to bolster university reputation and public perception.

Key words: PR campaigns, reputation, PR professionals, public perception, reputation management.

Аннотация. Данное статья исследует значимую роль, которую играют студенты в формировании репутации и усилиях по публичным отношениям (PR) университетов. Анализируя влияние студенческих мероприятий, организаций и проектов на общий образ образовательных учреждений, это статья стремится пролить свет на влияние вовлеченности студентов на управление репутацией университета. Через всесторонний анализ участия студентов в различных внеклассных мероприятиях, социальных проектах и PR-кампаниях, это статья стремится выявить ключевые стратегии и успешные кейс-стади, демонстрирующие, как студенты могут эффективно способствовать улучшению репутации своих университетов. Подчеркивая важность взаимодействия студентов с обществом и их роль как бренд-посланников своих учреждений, это статья предоставляет ценные знания для администраторов университетов, специалистов по PR и самих студентов о том, как использовать инициативы студентов для укрепления репутации университета и общественного восприятия.

Ключевые слова: PR-кампании, репутация, специалисты по связям с общественностью, общественное восприятие, управление репутацией.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada talabalarining universitetlar obro‘si va jamoatchilik bilan aloqalar (PR) harakatlarini shakllantirishdagi roli o‘rganiladi. Talabalar faoliyati, tashkilotlari va loyihalarining ta‘lim muassasalarining umumiy imidjiga ta‘sirini tahlil qilinib, talabalarining ishtiroki universitet obro‘sini boshqarishga qanday ta‘sir o‘tkazishi haqida yoritiladi. Talabalarining turli darsdan tashqari mashg‘ulotlar, ijtimoiy loyihalar va PR-kampaniyalardagi ishtirokini har tomonlama tahlil qilish orqali ushbu maqolada talabalarining o‘z universitetlari obro‘sini yaxshilashga qanday samarali hissa qo‘shishini ko‘rsatadigan asosiy strategiyalar va muvaffaqiyatli ish bosqichlari aniqlashtiriladi. Talabalarining jamiyat bilan o‘zaro munosabatlari va ularning o‘z muassasalarining brend elchisi sifatidagi roli ta‘kidlanib, universitet ma‘murlari, PR mutaxassislari va talabalarining o‘zlari uchun universitet obro‘si va jamoatchilik idrokini

mustahkamlash uchun talabalar tashabbuslaridan qanday foydalanish bo‘yicha qimmatli bilimlarni taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *PR kampaniyalari, obro‘- e‘tibor, jamoatchilik bilan aloqalar bo‘yicha mutaxassislar, jamoatchilik fikri, obro‘-e‘tiborni boshqarish.*

Universities strive for academic excellence, and a strong reputation is a key component of achieving this goal. While faculty research, curriculum development, and infrastructure investments are often the focus on university ranking systems, the active engagement of students in intellectual pursuits can significantly contribute to the institutional reputation and performance. In this article, we explore the ways in which students’ involvement in academic projects, research opportunities, and intellectual endeavors can enhance a university’s reputation and contribute to its overall performance. Reputation is an important and critical factor that has a huge effect on the sustainability of a college or university. When their reputation is good, academic institutions can gain a competitive advantage¹.

There are can be several ways that students can support improving university’s reputation and impact its general image among public. First and furthest, students who participate in academic projects and research opportunities can contribute to the university’s research output, enhancing its reputation for intellectual rigor. These experiences allow students to work closely with faculty mentors, contributing to the expansion of knowledge in their field and potentially leading to publications, presentations at conferences, and other forms of recognition.

Participating in academic projects and research opportunities offers various benefits for students beyond the expansion of knowledge in their field. These experiences can also lead to valuable networking opportunities, as students work alongside faculty mentors and other researchers in their discipline. These connections can prove invaluable in the academic and professional worlds, providing opportunities for collaborations, recommendations, and future career advancement. More and more institutions of higher learning are now crafting various strategies to build better reputations, increase satisfaction, and establish loyalty among their students².

Moreover, involvement in research projects can help students develop essential skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and effective communication. These skills not only enhance their academic performance but also prepare them for success in their future careers. To remain internationally competitive, colleges and universities are expanding their academic offerings and improving their service quality by boosting their reputation to attract prospective learners³. Universities place a high value on research output, as it is a significant factor in their reputation and ranking. Students who contribute to this output through their participation in research projects can help to strengthen the university’s position in the academic community.

Additionally, research experiences can lead to tangible outcomes, such as publications, patents, or other forms of intellectual property. These accomplishments can further increase a university’s reputation and attract more funding, students, and faculty. Thus, academic projects

¹ Moto, G., Del-Castillo-Feito, C., & Blanco-Gonzalez, A. (2020). Reputation and legitimacy: Key factors for Higher Education Institutions’ sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Business Research*, 112, 342-353.

² Kaushal, V., & Ali, N. (2019). University reputation, brand attachment and brand personality as antecedents of student loyalty: A study in higher education context. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 23, 254-266.

³ Khoshtaria, T., Datuashvili, D., & Matin, A. (2020). The impact of brand equity dimensions on university reputation: an empirical study of Georgian higher education. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 30(2), 239-255.

and research opportunities offer students numerous benefits, including the expansion of knowledge, valuable networking, skill development, and the chance to contribute to the university’s research output and reputation. Following that there is huge work of PR campaign behind these to show up to public and build bridge between them.

Past studies identified sources of student satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Among these were: faculty services, academic experience, student support facilities, campus life, and social integration⁴, facilities, job prospects, cost of studying, and reputation⁵, lecturers, program, assessment and feedback, resources, technology, facilities, and social life⁶, teaching method, administration, enrollment, and infrastructures⁷.

Besides this, collaborative learning experiences can also possibly contribute to a positive reputation for universities. Collaborative learning refers to educational approaches where students work together in groups to learn. Examples include group projects, study groups, and intellectual discourse, among others.

Firstly, these learning experiences promote intellectual rigor. Students must engage in critical thinking, communication, and problem-solving when working together in groups. This not only enhances their academic abilities but also prepares them for the real world.

Secondly, collaborative learning experiences contribute to academic excellence by promoting a deeper understanding of course material. Students benefit from learning from one another’s strengths, weaknesses, and perspectives, enhancing the overall educational experience. For example, in Uzbekistan National University in order to closely connect theoretical knowledge with practice, the material and technical base of 3 field-practice areas, 32 flow-scientific laboratories, 3 flow-scientific-experimental centers, 1 Inter-University Scientific Laboratory and 2 unique objects are being improved. At the same time, the work of attracting student-youth to scientific activities, participation in grant competitions and projects, training of targeted scientific personnel for other higher education and research institutions continues consistently⁸. This is implemented for students to build huge bridge between their knowledge and experience, moreover, collaborative learning experiences can lead to increased student satisfaction and a strong sense of community. Students appreciate the opportunity to engage with their peers, learn from one another, and develop relationships that last beyond the classroom. According to Jean Paolo G. Lacap and Jaime V. Cortez’s study, satisfaction has an indirect effect on the relationship between Higher Education Institution reputation and student loyalty⁹. Thus, collaborative learning experiences are essential for fostering a culture of intellectual rigor and academic excellence on campus. They promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and deep understanding of course material, contributing to a positive reputation for universities and a rewarding educational

⁴ Martirosyan, N. (2015). An examination of factors contributing to student satisfaction in Armenian higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 29(2), 177-191.

⁵ Hanssen, T., & Solvoll, G. (2015). The importance of university facilities for student satisfaction at a Norwegian University. *Facilities*, 33(13/14) 744-759.

⁶ Wilkins, S., & Balakrishnan, M. S. (2013). Assessing student satisfaction in transnational higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 27(2), 143-156.

⁷ Navarro, M., Iglesias, M., & Torres, P. (2005). A new management element for universities: Satisfaction with the offered courses. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 19(6), 505-526

⁸ <https://nuu.uz/university/>

⁹ Jean Paolo G. Lacap and Jaime V. Cortez’s (2023) Does Reputation Lead to Student Loyalty? The Case of a Private Does Reputation Lead to Student Loyalty? The Case of a Private Higher Education Institution, a State University, and a Local Higher Education Institution, a State University, and a Local College/The South East Asian Journal of Management Volume-17, (31-32)

experience for students. On the other perspective, sometimes students can play as a good PR manager role to build an image of university, satisfying the opportunities and using collaborative learning experiences.

Considering all aspects, which is mentioned above, it is also essential that academic achievements, such as high grades, academic awards, and other forms of recognition, can contribute significantly to a university’s reputation for academic excellence. Universities with a track record of producing high-achieving students can attract top faculty, students, and research funding, further enhancing their reputation and performance. Meanwhile, academic achievements are a crucial aspect of a university’s reputation for academic excellence. Students who excel academically bring prestige to their institutions, contributing to the university’s overall standing in academic rankings and the public eye. High grades, academic awards, and other forms of recognition are essential indicators of a student’s mastery of their field of study and their potential for future success.

Universities that consistently produce high-achieving students are particularly attractive to top faculty, who seek to work and collaborate with the best and brightest minds. These faculty members bring valuable expertise and knowledge to the institution, contributing to an intellectual community that fosters academic excellence. In operationalizing the construct of reputation, Telci and Kantur found that reputable institutions have the following characteristics:

- 1) they have high academic quality;
- 2) they are well-established and recognised;
- 3) they are innovative and offer several physical and social advancement opportunities;
- 4) they are managed by a successful head; and
- 5) they are responsible to its external and internal stakeholders, including the environment¹⁰.

As QS ranking judge university ranking as 40%, academic quality can include main part of reputation and it is really up to professors’ and students’ academic ratio.

Moreover, academic achievements can also attract top students to a university. Prospective students and their families look to academic rankings and the achievements of current students as indicators of a university’s quality and value. By producing high-achieving students, universities can build a reputation as a place of academic excellence, attracting a more competitive and talented student body.

Research funding is another crucial aspect of academic excellence, as research is a critical component of advancing knowledge and solving real-world problems. Universities with a strong reputation for academic excellence are more likely to secure research grants and funding, allowing them to invest in cutting-edge research projects and facilities.

Furthermore, academic achievements can have a ripple effect, creating a self-reinforcing cycle of excellence. High-achieving students are more likely to go on to successful careers and contribute to society in meaningful ways, while top faculty continue to produce groundbreaking research and attract new talent to the institution. This cycle of excellence helps to solidify a university’s reputation for academic excellence and sets it apart from its competitors.

In conclusion, academic achievements are a fundamental aspect of a university's reputation for academic excellence. By producing high-achieving students, universities can attract top faculty, students, and research funding, further enhancing their reputation and performance

¹⁰ Telci, E. & Kantur, D. (2014). University reputation: Scale development and validation. *Bogazici Journal Review of Social, Economic, and Administrative Studies*, 28(2), 49-74.

and students play a vital role in fueling a university’s reputation and performance. By providing students with opportunities to engage in intellectual pursuits and academic excellence, universities can attract top students and faculty, secure research funding, and build a strong and positive reputation for academic rigor. For PR managers aiming to enhance a university's reputation, prioritizing and promoting student collaborative learning initiatives alongside highlighting academic achievements can significantly boost the institution's standing. By showcasing the dynamic and interactive learning environment that fosters teamwork and academic excellence, PR managers can effectively communicate the university's commitment to holistic education and student success. Emphasizing the synergy between collaborative learning and academic accomplishments not only elevates the institution's image but also underscores its dedication to cultivating well-rounded graduates prepared for future challenges in a competitive academic landscape.

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